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Gopikrishnan Kottoor's *This Small Town: New Poems*

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***This Small Town: New Poems* | Poetry | Gopikrishnan Kottoor |
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"My religion is love..." wrote John Keats, more than two centuries ago.

Here is another poet who might well claim the same. As in almost all his numerous collections of poetry, love is the theme of a sizeable number of poems in his latest collection as well.

To Gopikrishnan, the forms of Nature are most often metaphors for facets of romantic love or its loss. The poet rides to the starry sky, makes the wind sigh through the trees, causes flowers to wilt and die, creates birdsong - all in the name of love.

Daringly original figurative language is his forte. The Metaphysical Poets would have welcomed him into their midst! He is a master of metaphor.

A notable feature of his love poems is the dying fall at the close. It is startling, often searing.

The later poems in 'This Small Town' take us to many a small town. Here, other themes like suffering, death and transience take over.

His poems about creatures big and small are remarkable for their detailing and near-empathy.

A poem like "The Back of the Crucifix" is sufficient to show that Gopikrishnan's poetic powers are as strong as ever:

"No one can see the back of the Crucifix.
It is plain, where the bird droppings,
the lichen has long lain.
But that's where the nails have gone
deep, deep in."

It says little while saying much as true poetry does.